

7(*t*)] succumbed to the disease in all test locations. RIL 45 and 249, presumably carrying *Pi 5(t)*, showed differential reactions to pathogen populations at Jorhat and Suttur, while RIL 77 was susceptible at all test sites, suggesting that this RIL may not have the *Pi 5(t)* gene. LTH (Li-jiang-xin-tuan-hei-gu) near-isogenic lines that were susceptible at Cuttack varied in their reac-

tions at other locations, particularly in the eastern (Jorhat) and southern (Suttur) regions.

Of the four gene combinations evaluated, the one with *Pi 1(t)* and *Pi 4(t)* was susceptible to blast at Jagadapur, Almora, and Jorhat. The combination with *Pi 1(t)* and *Pi 2(t)* was resistant in all locations except Suttur, while that with *Pi 2(t)*

and *Pi 4(t)* was effective in all six test locations. Our results clearly showed the usefulness of resistance genes in different locations.

Reference

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Usefulness of combinations of bacterial blight resistance genes at Cuttack, Orissa, India

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Although 19 bacterial blight resistance genes have been identified so far (Kinoshita 1991), precise information on their compatibility or incompatibility with local pathogen populations is essential for designing breeding programs for resistant varieties. We evaluated the effectiveness of known bacterial blight resistance genes singly and in combination under field conditions against local populations of the pathogen in a trap nursery under irrigated conditions during the 1998 wet season.

Twenty near-isogenic lines in the IR24 background, 11 of them carrying single known resistance genes and the remaining nine possessing various combinations of these genes, along with an *Oryza minuta* derivative line (WHD-IS-78-1-5) and Malagkit Sungsong were tested (see table). IR24 and Karuna (Co 33) were included as susceptible checks. For each entry, 44 hills were planted per row, with 20-cm spacing between plants and rows. Two replications were maintained in a completely randomized design. Each replication consisting of four rows of the test entries was flanked on either side with a single row of the local susceptible check Karuna. Fertilizer was applied to supply 80 kg N ha⁻¹, half basally and half at the pre-tillering stage. No pesticide was applied. The fields were kept clean by hand-weeding twice.

Plants were exposed to natural infection by bacterial blight. Bacterial blight started to appear at tillering and continued to spread vertically until the crop heading stage. Both the intensity of vertical susceptibility (denoted by multiples of S [see table] and quantitative reactions to bacte-

rial blight (based on the 0–9 scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice*, SES, IRRI 1996) were recorded at the milk stage. Levels 1–5 covering 1–25% of leaf blade infection are considered resistant, while levels 7–9 are considered susceptible.

Reaction of near-isogenic lines carrying bacterial blight resistance genes singly and in combination, Cuttack, Orissa, India.

Variety/line	Resistance gene	Bacterial blight reaction	
		Vertical susceptibility ^a	0–9 SES scale ^b
Karuna (local susceptible check)	nd ^c	SSSS	9
IR24 (susceptible check)	<i>Xa18</i>	SSS	9
WHD-IS-78-1-5	<i>Xa23</i>	R	5
WHD-IS-78-1-5 (<i>O. minuta</i> derivative)	<i>Xa23</i>	R	5
Malagkit Sungsong	<i>Xa3</i>	R	5
IRBB1	<i>Xa1</i>	SSS	7
IRBB3	<i>Xa3</i>	SSS	7
IRBB4	<i>Xa4</i>	SSS	7
IRBB5	<i>xa5</i>	R	5
IRBB7	<i>Xa7</i>	SSS	7
IRBB8	<i>xa8</i>	R	3
IRBB10	<i>Xa10</i>	SSS	7
IRBB11	<i>Xa11</i>	SSS	7
IRBB13	<i>xa13</i>	R	5
IRBB14	<i>Xa14</i>	SSS	7
IRBB21	<i>Xa21</i>	R	1
AY4 + 5-2	<i>Xa4</i> + <i>xa5</i>	R	3
NH8-15-1-5	<i>Xa4</i> + <i>xa13</i>	R	3
NH9-52-1-4	<i>Xa4</i> + <i>Xa21</i>	R	1
NH11-21-1-3	<i>xa5</i> + <i>xa13</i>	R	1
NH12-17-2-4	<i>xa5</i> + <i>Xa21</i>	R	1
NH15-51-1-3	<i>xa13</i> + <i>Xa21</i>	R	1
NH21-37-1-1	<i>Xa4</i> + <i>xa5</i> + <i>xa13</i>	R	3
NH24-10-1-3	<i>Xa4</i> + <i>xa5</i> + <i>Xa21</i>	R	1
NH56-1-44-4	<i>Xa4</i> + <i>xa5</i> + <i>xa13</i> + <i>Xa21</i>	R	1

^aDenotes intensity of vertical susceptibility of plants (susceptible reaction of 7 restricted to 1/4 (S), 1/2 (SS), 3/4 (SSS), almost all leaves infected (SSSS); reactions of less than 7 are considered as resistant (R)). ^b0–9 scale (SES) for field test, lesion area: 1, 1–5%; 3, 6–12%; 5, 13–25%; 7, 26–50%; 9, 51–100% (reactions of 1–5 are considered as resistant, while 7 and above are susceptible). ^cnd = not detected.

Bacterial blight incidence was uniform in the fields. The susceptible checks showed a disease rating of 9 in the SES. The vertical spread of the disease within hills, however, was maximum in Karuna when compared with IR24. Interestingly, Malagkit Sungsong and the *O. minuta* derivative exhibited a susceptible rating of 5, despite their being resistant in earlier years. IRBB5 and IRBB13, carrying *xa5* and *xa13*, respectively, also showed a similar degree of susceptibility. Lines possessing *Xa1*, *Xa3*, *Xa4*, *Xa7*, *Xa10*, *Xa11*, and *Xa14* individually were all distinctly susceptible to the disease. On the other hand, genes *xa8* and *Xa21* were singly effective in resisting bacterial blight, exhibiting a score of 1. All the gene combinations (see table) were resistant, presumably because of in-

teraction or quantitative complementation between resistance genes (Yoshimura et al 1995, Huang et al 1997). This study points out that, even though a particular gene is ineffective singly against bacterial blight (for example, *Xa4*, *Xa5*, and *xa13*), its combination with another resistance gene (*Xa4 + xa5*, *Xa4 + xa13*, *xa5 + xa13*, *Xa4 + xa5 + xa13*) conferred resistance. The combination *xa5* and *xa13* was relatively superior to the other combinations (Huang et al 1997). All combinations carrying *Xa21* were also resistant. In this case, resistance may be attributed to the presence of *Xa21*, which individually conferred resistance. Deploying multiple genes together may lessen the possibility of rapid pathogen adaptation to cultivars carrying single resistance genes.

References

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Thrips infestation in relation to panicle stage in rice

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Thrips incidence at the panicle stage in rice was investigated because such information would be useful in (a) timing plant protection measures and (b) getting correct samples to estimate the thrips population on the crop. The infestation of panicle thrips, *Haplothrips ganglbaueri* Schmutz, was studied in variety Pusa 169 grown un-

der transplanted and irrigated conditions during kharif (monsoon) in 1997 and 1998 (see table).

One-month-old seedlings were transplanted in the main field in the second week of July each year. Thrips incidence was observed in panicles of different ages—(a) emerging panicles with their

basal portion still in the leaf sheath, (b) freshly emerged panicles, and (c) panicles in the milky stage. In each category, 25 panicles were observed for thrips population counts. The panicle was enclosed in a polythene bag and shaken gently to dislodge the thrips. Sampling was done once in 1997 and three times in 1998 at 5-d in-

Incidence of *Haplothrips ganglbaueri* Schmutz on panicles of different ages in variety Pusa 169, New Delhi, India, 1997-98.

Panicle stage	Season							
	1997 kharif				1998 kharif			
	1st sampling (70 DAT) ^a		1st sampling (65 DAT)		2nd sampling (70 DAT)		3rd sampling (75 DAT)	
	Population panicle ⁻¹	Population range	Population panicle ⁻¹	Population range	Population panicle ⁻¹	Population range	Population panicle ⁻¹	Population range
Emerging panicle	2.10 (1.22) ^b	0–5	0.40 (0.27)	0–2	3.15 (1.56)	0–10	1.95 (1.11)	0–8
Freshly emerged panicle	5.00 (2.03)	2–9	1.20 (0.98)	0–3	6.00 (2.28)	0–12	4.2 (1.94)	0–10
Panicle in milky stage	0.40 (0.36)	0–2	0.25 (0.22)	0–2	0.45 (0.39)	0–2	0.05 (0.05)	0–1
SE±	(0.24)		(0.16)		(0.23)		(0.20)	
CD (5%)	(0.48)		(0.33)		(0.46)		(0.42)	
CD (1%)	(0.65)		(0.44)		(0.62)		(0.56)	

^aDAT = days after transplanting. ^bNumbers in parentheses are square root-transformed values of original thrips counts.